

INCREASING THE ROLE OF LITERATURE AND ART IN IMPROVING THE LIVING CULTURE OF THE POPULATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13628687>

Abstract. *In this article, the importance of literature and art in the formation of social standards in society, the role of art education in the formation of human personality is analyzed in detail based on the theoretical views of Eastern and Western classical scientists.*

Keywords: *society, people, literature, art, social norm, musical education, musical art, education, thinking, imagination, culture of life.*

Cultural and educational activity is divided into individual, group and public forms according to the nature of the subjects participating in it. A specific form is suitable for each type of cultural educational activity, reading, familiarization with works of applied art is an individual form of generalization of works of art.

The art of music is a great source of thought. Perfect mental development of a person cannot be achieved without musical education. As our sages say, “Musical education is not the education of a musicologist, but first of all, the education of a person”. On the basis of musical education, a person has the idea that nobility, beauty are not only in the external world, but also inner world. Music is a powerful source of self-education. Everyone knows that today it is difficult to imagine life without music.

Stendhal, a classic of world literature, expressed the following opinion about music: “Music is the only art capable of penetrating the depths of the human soul and expressing its experiences...” [2.-P. 83.]

In fact, music not only expresses the most subtle aspects of human existence, but also teaches people about concepts such as life, death, love, and compassion.

In the works of the great thinker Jalaluddin Rumi: “Nothing in the world can reveal the hidden powers of the human soul like music and dance, music can free it from the petty worries of life and start towards its spiritual world... music is like a woman. When you use her as a servant, you put a person to sleep and wake up an animal. But you can love him, join him and flow in one wave, and in this way you can take the first step to awaken the true human essence in your soul...” [3.-P. 36-37.]

Nowadays, it cannot be said that the interest in music among our youth arises with deep thinking and deep artistic and aesthetic feelings. Because many young people are used to listening to entertainment music.

Even the great thinker Abdullakh Dehlavi, who lived and created several centuries ago, noticed the negative consequences of the era of entertainment music that was listened to only for the purpose of time. In the work “Tahiku-s-samo” ... according to the scientist, as long as music is within the scope of worldly pleasures, it really makes the human soul go into heedlessness and indifference, out of awareness. According to the scholars who followed Dehlavi, “Aishu Ishrat is the prayer of Satan” [3.-P. 39.].

In fact, entertaining light musical works immediately hit the stomach, lose their charm, cannot teach logical thinking and understanding of the essence of life. “If my listeners listened to my music only for a moment, I would be very sorry, because I tried to improve the human soul spiritually”, said Handel about his work.

D. Kobalevski addressed the participants of the 9th conference of the International society for music education and noted the following: “Use up the time of young people, but do not suffocate them, do not steal their spiritual world, don’t miss out on the joy of interacting with the great art of the past and present. Get the youth used to learning from great people. Explain to them that regardless of the genre and form of any work, it should always correspond to a high level of aesthetic taste, that the aesthetic basis embodies not only artistry, but also idealism and spirituality”. [4. -P. 72-73.].

In fact, the high or low, fine or coarse, sharp or dull, good or bad taste of the spirit plays an important role in human life. The spiritual strength of taste does not allow the unconscious to follow various negative currents in art. A person with perfect spiritual taste is not only a person who understands the masterpieces of art, he appreciates the beauty of life in any form - whether it is in nature, manners, work, or in the objects around him. In this sense, Charles Louis Montesque’s phrase “Taste is a condensed mind” is not without reason.

Nowadays, great positive changes are taking place in the life of music art in the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, the regular holding of the International Festival “Sharq Taronalari”, which has become a tradition, is an art holiday for our people. For example, in 1997, 267 people from thirty-two countries and two international organizations took part in the festival, which started on August 26. By today, the number of participating countries has exceeded one hundred.

International Music Festival “Sharq Taronalari” is aimed at strengthening of friendship between peoples, world peace, wide promotion of friendship and harmony between peoples;

developing the musical arts of the peoples of the East and further increasing its importance, covering the traditions of musical art of the peoples of Uzbekistan and other countries, having close scientific and creative dialogues and cooperation with them;

preservation of the traditions of musical art of Eastern countries, further development of cultural communication.

conducting scientific studies and researches in the field of traditional music of the peoples of the East, sharing experiences, organizing roundtable discussions, presentations and master classes.

In order to set the musical education of young people on the right track, a collection titled “Problems of music creativity” was published, which discusses about the problems of composers, musicologists and music science of our Republic. This work is dedicated to the life and creative legacy of artists who made a great contribution to Uzbek music of the 20th century - Y. Rajabiy, K. Jabborov, F. Sodikov, S. Kalonov, M. Ashrafiy. We believe that these works will successfully serve as an active educational guide for improving the musical knowledge of young people in the future.

Today, the need for verbal fiction that skillfully expresses the human spirit, goals and aspirations, changes in his mind and life is stronger than ever.

As long as independent Uzbekistan is recognized at the world level, its new literature should have a corresponding position. The future perspective of the great nation's literature is related to the artistic education of the growing young generation.

Fiction has long been considered an art that educates human thinking with great ideas. Fiction is an educational tool that fills the heart of the student with high thoughts, has the opportunity to talk with them about life's concerns, give advice, and make friends with the student from the heart. The meaning of communicating with fiction is that it enriches the reader's life experience by introducing him to a new, different essence of life. This is primarily the life of the creator of the work, the artist.

In the work, the writer reflects the exciting thoughts of thousands of his contemporaries, as well as tells about the dreams, longings, sufferings and joys of thousands of people. For this reason, the student will have the life meaning and experience of thousands of people, his perception will be familiar with the spiritual experience of generations.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences O. Musurmonova explains such educational qualities of fiction as follows: "Literature provides knowledge, image-information, heuristic (creative thinking), spiritual, social, educational. Its specific aspects, such as a symptom, comfort, and interaction, directly serve to ensure the increase of its educational capabilities". [5. -P. 93.].

We can not say that young people are reading a lot of books today, when young people are surrounded by books with pictures and without pictures, decorative and cheerful, modest and serious, from unique historical books to the smell of the printing press. Many young people prefer to watch TV than to read books. This is due to the fact that television and radio have emerged as a huge competitive factor for the press. However, according to the information published by Russian scientists recently, the left hemispheres of our children, who watch TV for hours all day, are gradually not fully developed.

According to some writers and experts, the low quality of children's literature is the main reason for the decline in reading. In our opinion, this is also a one-sided view. It is true that children's literature also suffered a certain crisis during the years of recession. Our life consisted of hymns and praises. Children's literature is no exception. In our opinion, these are all interrelated problems and it is necessary to consider them in depth and solve them comprehensively. It can be said that these problems depend primarily on the creativity of artists. In order to overcome the artistic crisis in reading a book, the writer should be the heart, soul, and light of the eyes in relation to the times.

"A writer, Honore de Balzac, should be able to express the entire universe in one word, the entire philosophical system in one image," he expressed.

The two sides of raising the level of reading are the necessity of careful and knowledgeable teaching of literature classes even in secondary schools. For this, first of all, the teacher should have a deep understanding of the ideology of independence and artistically educate students who believe in the future of our country and who can contribute to its development with their knowledge and hard work. This requires the teacher to be a knowledgeable specialist of his subject, to be armed with knowledge of other sciences, to be a teacher-educator and a careful psychologist.

According to some scientists: "Each lesson has a specific goal in mind. In particular, literature classes differ from other subjects in terms of their educational impact. Therefore, it would not be wrong to say that literature has assumed the responsibility of filling this spiritual void. The educational and upbringing value of literature classes is determined by this". [6.-P- 106.]

Therefore, humanity, justice, stewardship, work and craft, attitude towards parents, women, modesty, equality, generosity, correct speech, love and loyalty are taught in literature classes; friendship, hospitality, modesty, decency, purity, education are available. Because the

above ideas are put forward at the base of any classic art work. During the lesson, the analysis of these aspects of human virtue will undoubtedly leave its place in the student's artistic thinking and lead to the formation of his artistic culture in a beautiful form.

So, in recent years, scientists have developed a methodology for studying literature in connection with other social sciences. For example, it was found that studying the art of words - literature, art of painting - fine art, visual art - music art will make a qualitative contribution to the artistic culture of the student. In this way, the student can be taught to identify similarities between the works of a writer and an artist, a writer and a composer, and an artist and a composer.

The process of independence created a very large and important social-political, cultural-ideological basis for building a democratic society in our country. At the same time, the government of our country and members of the society came to the conclusion that independence cannot be strengthened without cultural and educational aspects, turning independence into reality, a certain social event that is guaranteed to be fulfilled. It is becoming clear to everyone that all socio-economic, political, moral and ideological reforms taking place in society can reach their perfection only through cultural means.

The fact that spiritual factors have become a priority today is also due to the democratic processes taking place in society. In fact, culture is a social force that further enlivens democracy, gives it creative power, and ultimately creates profound positive changes in the life of the society. Their harmony is the basis of a fair and just state.

One of the main reasons for paying special attention to the activities of cultural and educational institutions is the special attitude of the government of Uzbekistan to this issue. After all, economic growth and development are the body of our society, and the maturity of spirituality and political consciousness is its soul, mind and soul. In order to achieve our great country and great future, we need to educate intelligent, enlightened people who are proud of their past, great values, nation and believe in the future. [1.-P.261.]

People missed the circle of makomologists, debates and discussions. From this point of view, the resolution of President Shavkat Mirziyoev of November 17, 2017 "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national makom", which was adopted in order to solve existing problems and raise the status of the art of makom at the national and international levels. It's done. The Art Center of Uzbek national makom, established in accordance with the decision, has been entrusted with huge tasks and responsibilities. Starting from 2018, the organization of the International makom art conference every two years in the city of Shakhrisabz will undoubtedly be a great impetus to the development of Makom.

For the purpose of preservation of the national art of our people, wide promotion of its unique examples, development of love and affection for art in the hearts of the young generation, strengthening of friendship and brotherhood between peoples, further increase of the prestige of the art of makom on a world scale, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to prepare for the II international makom art conference" was adopted.

The resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 17, 2017, "On measures for the further development of Uzbek national makom art" and dated April 6, 2018, "On the International makom art conference" were announced. According to them, it was decided to organize an international makom art conference every two years in the city of Shakhrisabz, and the proposals to hold such an event on September 6-10, 2018 for the first time were approved.

Summing up from the above, it should be noted that the very important task of improving the activity of cultural and educational institutions, in particular, cultural centers and cultural palaces, libraries, increasing their efficiency, was recognized as a priority direction of our country's development. Unlike cultural and educational institutions during the Soviet era, the working style of these cultural centers changed during the years of independence. It was especially important to clarify the goals and objectives of such institutions. On this basis, the determination of the main goal of cultural-educational institutions, which is to achieve the spiritual maturity of a wide range of citizens and the social, spiritual and moral unity of the society, in the course of conducting activities based on national and universal values, was in line with the requirements of today's development strategy of New Uzbekistan.

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